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Green Banking
Perceptions and
Challenges

Editors
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Dr. Sandeep S. Shenoy

Dept. of Commerce
University College, Hampankatta, Mangaluru
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Green Banking: A New Trend in Bhatkal Co-operative Banking Scenario

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Abstract—The world has seen much focus on economic progress and Bank is also not the exception for this. This paper tries to find out the ways to Go Green through 'Green Banking'. Green banking is like a standard bank which considered all the environmental or ecological and social factor with an aim to protect environment and concern natural resources. It is also called as an ethical bank or a sustainable bank. This study is mainly based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from Co-operative sector banks to identify the initiatives taken by the banks for changing their activities, products and process green. It is very important for the co-operative banks to accelerate and pro-active the rate of the growth of the economy the banks face the instance competition in the global market as there is a continuous changes in the environmental factors.

Keywords: Green Banking, Challenges, Progress, Initiative, Co-operative Banks

INTRODUCTION

A green banking is also a financial facilities just like a normal banking. High morality or ethics of the banks is to protect the environment through its daily business activities. Financing will be provided to only such business and innovation which protects and enhance the environment. Also these banks motivates the entrepreneurs through recognition and appreciation for clean, energy, rainwater harvesting, solar energy etc.

Why green banking is important?

- Average yearly increase in global temperature since 1880=0.07Deg.c
- Average yearly increase in global temperature since 1970=0.17Deg.c
- Average yearly increase in global temperature since 2011-2015=0.23Deg.c
- Hottest month recorded on the earth=July 2016
- Reduction in Arctic sea ice per decade=13.3%
- Annual rise in sea level since 1993=3.39mn
- Number of weather related death from 1995 to 2015 6,00,000(30,000 per day)

Do you think money will be give you environment? To enjoy hard earned money we need clean environment without is ZERO. So any initiative by anyone in any form to protect the environment should be treated and respected on high priority or else we are going to leave:

1. Zero clean water

2. Zero clean air
3. Zero clean land

MEANING OF GREEN BANKING

Green banking is like a standard bank which considered all the environmental or ecological and social factor with an aim to protect environment and concern natural resources. It is also called as an ethical bank or a sustainable bank. Green banking also mean promoting environmental friendly practices in bank. But that can be promoted in all institution in general the green banking can be define in a number of ways in a broader prospective. It is environmental friendly banking practice that promote their customer to reduce the carbon footprint through their banking practices. "The Indian Bank association defines it as green bank function like a standard bank which considering the environment and social factor of natural resources".

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To Study the Green Banking Concept.
2. To study the different products and services provided by the Co-Operative banks under green banking.
3. To Understand the Challenges Of Green Banking at Bhatkal
4. To Know the Benefits of Green banking
5. To study the Green Banking Initiative taken by Bhatkal co-operative bank
6. To know the Progress and working of urban co-operative banks in Bhatkal taluk

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive research design is developed for conducting the study. It is mainly based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from Co-operative sector banks to identify the initiatives taken by the banks for changing their activities, products and process green. The secondary data were collected from websites of banks, annual report, journals etc.

CHALLENGES OF GREEN BANKING AT BHATKAL

1. Education and Awareness:
 - Paper education should be provided to the public for utilizing the banking technology.
 - Creating an awareness for the importance of environment.
 - Confidence building.
 - Un-educate and poor people may get trapped.

2. Security and confidentiality
 - Importance of PIN number. Use ID On Time Password(OPT), token password
 - Reporting of lost card, lost phone on theft of cards and mobile to respective authorized authorities
 - Free SMS and phone callasking for PIN number
3. Network
 - Effective and strong network all over Bhatkal

BENEFITS OF GREEN BANKING AT BHATKAL

1. Sign up for online banking

Sign up for online banking and go paperless. You will make your life easier and more secure not only will you reduce the waste by eliminating a paper statement from your life. By doing the online banking, your statement will be in one easy to access location and it will be protected by the security measures bank take to prevent the identity.

2. Receive your paycheck by direct deposit

Signup for the direct deposit and your paycheck will be automatically deposited into your account by rather than heading to the bank after payday. It will not only save your money and time by decreasing the amount of gas you may use on those numerous trips to the bank you can access your fund very quickly by using the direct deposit.

3. Utilize online bill pay service

Online banking stage whether through the various banks or by using directly the company's websites, signing up for the online bill payment service will reduce impact on the environment as you are not able to receive paper copies of your bill. In addition you can save money by sending your bill through mail.

4. Better risk management

It provides the benefits of better risk management to the banks. Better risk management helps in building good image of the banks and by thus reducing the reputational risk.

5. Convenient process

Green banking provides the convenience to the bank as well as bank customers. Due to the various banking initiative like ATM, online banking, mobile banking etc. the foot fall of the service of the customers reduce to the larger extent in the bank branches and this results in reduce effort and cost in the management of the bank activities. These banking activities provides convenience to the customer in terms of management, energy and fuel conservation as they need not visit the branch for every transaction.

GREEN BANKING INITIATIVE AT BHATKAL

By knowing the seriousness and importance of green banking. I strongly suggest following initiative for the Bhatkal based co-operative banks.

ONLINE BANKING

Bank transactions are performance at the convenient of the customers. Tools required are computer and internet connection with the user ID and password one can log into his account for required banking transaction like payment, deposit, transfer etc. Advantages of online banking mentioned below:

- Papers are manufactured from trees. Hence by the using online banking/transaction we can save trees which intern save the environment
- Faster and accurate transaction
- Easy tracking and monitoring

DEBIT CARD AND CREDIT CARD

Debit card and credit card us also known as plastic money. To use this card we need card reader at transaction point such as Petrol station, Hospitals, Malls, Toll plazas etc. Card is swiped for billed amount and 4 digit password is entered by the card holder. Customer sign over the receipt and retain duplicate receipt copy for his reference and original receipt will be retained by the service provider. Automatic instant SMS is sent for the registered mobile number for the said transaction.

A credit card is a plastic card which allow the card holder to buy the goods without making immediate payment/cash. The basic principle of credit card is “Buy now and pay later”. The seller send the bills to the concerned bank for payment and receives the amount.

Advantages for these are mentioned below

- Abusing of paper notes can be stopped completely
- Amount will be paid exactly to the billed amount including fraction. Hence change free transaction

MOBILE BANKING

Mobile banking is a service that allows the prospective customer to do the financial transaction through the mobile device like cellphone, tablet etc. This service is provided by the bank or any other financial institution.

It is similar to online banking but with the use of mobile and mobile application. Mobile banking app is downloaded in the customer mobile account is logged by entering the customers ID and mobile PIN number which is sent to registered mobile number in the account. Its very handy and user friendly.

Advantages of these are mentioned below:

- Paperless banking
- Easy and convenient banking
- Account statement available at tip of finger

ELECTRONIC FUND TRANSFER(EFT)

Facility of electronically transferring money from one account to another account or other bank by particular bank is called EFT. Facilities such as NEFT(National Electronic Fund transfer), RTGS(Real-Time Gross Settlement system). Customer to walk into the bank where he has an account and after filling the required forms, required EFT is carried out with customers approval.

SUPPORT AND ENCOURAGE ENVIRONMENT FRIENDLY PROJECTS

Low interest rate on housing loan for “Solar powered” houses. Extended additional loan payment tenure for “Rain Water Harvesting” houses. Special interest rate for fishing boats which are equipped with the environmental friendly methodologies and practices like not throwing the oil to sea, not throwing any waste to sea, non-fishing of banned aquatic animal etc.

Interest free loan to “Organic Agriculture”.

PROGRESS AND WORKING OF URBAN CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN BHATKAL TALUK

BHATKAL URBAN CO-OPERATIVE BANK

- This is the first co-operative bank in Bhatkal. Which Introduced Debit Card and Credit Card Facilities to the customer. 90% of the customer using Debit card and 50% of the customer using Credit card Facility.
- Mobile banking facility is provided by this bank to the customers to get the banking and financial services with the help of the mobile telecommunication device. The customer can easily check account balance, cheque payment stop,get the accounting information etc through the mobile device.
- The bank also provides the ATM facility. A customer can easily carryout his banking transaction through the ATMs at any time. The customer can deposit and withdraw the cash and he can easily collect the account information.
- Through online banking by sitting at home customer can perform various task. Eg: online billing, online payment, online money transfer, maintenance of various data through internet server

ST. MILAGRES CO-OPERATIVE BHATKAL

- The major facility of online banking is provided by the bank so,the customers can easily operate their banking transaction sitting at home

- Now a days debit card is useful for every customer so, the bank provides debit card facilities and around 65% people are using debit card
- Mobile banking is a service that allows the prospective customer to do the financial transaction through the mobile device like cellphone, tablet etc. This service is provided by the bank or any other financial institution.
- Credit card are used by the customer to make the immediate payment after buying the goods and services
- EFT is the part of the core banking solution. Its become easy for the customer to transfer the fund from one place to another, one account o another account not by the real movement of cheques, draft etc by through the movement of electronic media.
- It provides ATM facilities at every corner of the town. Minimun 65% people are using the cards so that the customer can easily do their transaction.

JANATA CO-OPERATIVE BHATKAL

- This is also one of most important bank at Bhatkal taluk which provides the various services to their valuable customers. It provides the mobile banking services through which the customer can do their transactions by using mobile device. The particular mobile banking application which is given by the bank is download by the customer in their mobile phones. An entering the Id address to use mobile banking.
- Nowadays people giving the more importance to debit card and credit card at every financial sector. The bank provide the debit card and credit card facility to their customers so the customer can easily buy the goods and services without using the cash it will reduce the paper work.
- The bank also provides the online banking service. This tools requires computer internet connection and user have to log his id and password to do the transaction through the online banking. He can make the payment deposit and transfer of cash etc.
- Facility of electronically fund transferring are provided by this banks. Money can be transferred from one account to another account or one bank to another bank but it can't transfer with other commercial banks. The customer can transfer money from one co-operative bank to another co-operative bank.

K.D.C.C. CO-OPERATIVE BANK, BHATKAL

- Online banking is a major facility in modern era is provided by this bank so the customer can easily and smoothly operate their banking transaction by logging their ID and password.

- It offers the ATM facility in the Bhatkal taluk. Minimum 25% peoples are using the ATM cards under this bank.
- Debit card is also offered by this bank to its valuable customer. Minimum 35% of its customers using the debit cards to operate the transactions
- Mobile banking is introduced by this particular co-operative bank that allows its customers to conduct its financial transactions remotely using mobile device such as smart phones, notebooks, tablets etc.

SOME SUGGESTIONS

- Communicate the people in the society through press
- To spread news about green banking construct websites
- Educate people about green banking through E-learning programmers
- To make green banking as part of annual environment reports
- To train bank employees about green banking and thereby increase their skills to perform a specific job
- Bank can offer green fund facility for its customer those who like to invest in projects of environment friendly

CONCLUSION

Green banking refers to the initiative to encourage the environment friendly investment taken by the banks. Green banking is a concept and beautiful way of thinking towards future sustainability. It is very important for the co-operative banks to accelerate and pro-active the rate of the growth of the economy the banks face the instance competition in the global market as there is a continuous changes in the environmental factors. The bank want to the stringent public policies and strict law suits. Bank want to apply responsibility to their business model and to apply morality of sustainability operation and their financial activity become harder by adopting the eco-friendly environmental factors in their activities bank can recover the investments and make the polluted industries become environmental friendly. It is a time now that India takes some major actions to gradually adhere to the equator principle-guidelines that use environment sensitive parameters, apart from financial, to fund project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Neyati, Ahuja (2015), "Green Banking in India: A Review of Literature", *International Journal for Research in Management and Pharmacy*, Vol. 4, January, pp. 11–16.
- [2] Ashitha, Amin (2016), "Green Banking in India and Global Perspective–A Review", *International Journal of Management and Social Science Research Review*, Vol. 1.
- [3] Bahl, Sarita (2012), "Green Banking-The New Strategic Imperative", *Journal of Asian Research Consortium*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, February, pp. 176–185.

- [4] Bhardwaj, B.R. and Malhotra, A. (2013), "Green Banking Strategies: Sustainability through Corporate Entrepreneurship", *Greener Journal of Business and Management Studies*, Vol. 4, pp. 180–193.
- [5] Chaurasia, Kumar Ashis (2014), "Green Banking Practices in Indian Banks", Blue Square Publishing House, Vol. 1, February, pp. 41–54.
- [6] Equator Principles (2011), About Equator Principles, Available at <http://www.equatorprinciples.com/index.php/about-cp/aboutcp>.
- [7] <http://greenbankreport.com>
- [8] Mahesh, A.C., Nirosha, M. and Pavithra, V. (2016), "Recent Trends in Indian Banking-Green Banking Initiative in India", *International Journal of Science Technology and Management*, Vol. 5, February, pp. 369–374.
- [9] www.bucb.in
- [10] www.indianjournals.com
- [11] www.kanaradccb.com
- [12] www.milagrescooperative.com
- [13] www.rbi.org.in
- [14] www.wikipedia.com